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Entrepreneurship Education for the Acceleration of Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development in Africa

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Across the African continent, unemployment levels remain high despite increasing levels of tertiary education. According to the United Nations, there are approximately 200 million Africans aged between 15 and 24 that make up more than half of the unemployment statistics on the continent (Ighobor, 2017). Youth make up approximately 60% of all the continent's unemployed. In countries, such as Senegal, South Africa, Botswana, this figure jumps to

approximately 30-40% while in North Africa, the rate is more than 25% (Ighobor, 2017). In most African states, youth unemployment takes place at a rate more than twice that for adults. In the majority of African states, young women are determinedly affected by unemployment than their male counterparts. In the majority of cases, it is more difficult for young women to find decent employment than their male counterparts.

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This is despite having comparable experience and skills set. In addition, Africa's youth find it even more problematic to find work in places that pay good wages, provide a measure of job security or develop skills for career development (Page, 2013). Equally important is the problem of under-employment, often masking the extent of youth unemployment in many African states which require even greater attention and government intervention in dealing with the issue (Page, 2013).

All this comes at the backdrop of continued population growth which will only aggravate an already delicate situation and ongoing policy concern facing governments across the continent. It is thought that by 2050 the continent's youth population will increase by approximately 50% (Sow, 2018). By that period, Africa is expected to house the largest number of youths globally, making up nearly twice the young population of Oceania, Southeast Asia, South Asia and East Asia (Sow, 2018).

It is predicted that the global population will have grown by approximately 2.2 billion and half of those people will be Africans. The implications on the labour force will be significant if the current population trends continue.

As the continent's youth population are set to represent an important share of Africa's total population, the risks that can arise if this young population is not given the opportunities needed to better their economic standings could be devastating and dire for their governments. Indeed, countless risks such as mass migration, insecurity and instability would need to be dealt with by African leaders while emphasis need to be placed on the need to invest into young 's peoples skills upgrading, education to unlock innovation, productivity, thereby helping to reduce poverty and ensuring the continent's make headways in meeting their SDGs. One such training is entrepreneurship training and education.

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Entrepreneurship is increasingly viewed as an important factor for sustainable broad-based development in emerging markets given that new businesses created have the potential to accelerate innovation and introduce new competitors to existing structures, thus contributing to productivity and eventually decent employment creation as well as economic growth.

The potential of entrepreneurship to the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 8 on decent work and economic growth is undeniable and is well researched. This brief issue will examine a few important joint programs in the area of entrepreneurship education and their potential contribution to the attainment of the Agenda 2030 for sustainable development.

According to a recent study by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor in partnership with the Youth Business International, approximately 60 percent of 18 to 34-year-olds were confident about their business prospects and believed they had the skills to successfully start a business (Bosma, N and Kelley, D., 2018).

The report further showed that at 29, the continent has the highest number of young people involved in new businesses (Bosma, N and Kelley, D., 2018). While entrepreneurship is accelerating among the youth on the continent, there are still several important barriers that hinder continued growth and optimum.

Some factors range from inadequate funding, poor infrastructure and technology to networks and technical knowledge and expertise. Entrepreneurship education curriculum jointly developed and administered by technical institutes and private sector entities are increasingly viewed as central for the growth and development of the sector, particularly among the youth.

By offering practical and industry relevant information on the key concepts of enterprise development, entrepreneurship education jointly administered by multilateral institutions such as the United Nations, academia and the private sector could contribute towards creating a space where youth are more open

to entrepreneurship as a viable alternative to earning a sustainable living (Stephan, et. al, 2015).

It provides knowledge and technical know-how in terms of business plan development and aims to create an ecosystem map for corporates and start-ups, which will locate and connect various entrepreneurial service providers across the continent (Stephan, et. al, 2015). Young African entrepreneurs will have access to knowledge about how to acquire funding, implement their innovations, and network and pitch their innovative ideas.

The United Nations Development Programme in partnership with Accenture, a multinational professional services company that provides services in strategy, digital technology, consulting and operations to establish YAS!, an online entrepreneurship portal-platform gears towards African youth population groups. Its objective is to cultivate a mind-set of employment generation and individual businesses that could contribute to the continent's sustainable development

efforts in helping to realize the Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development. The online platform, which serves the entire continent, addresses for main pillars of entrepreneurship, essentially mentorship, information, network and funding. The initiative targets young entrepreneurs and start-ups as well as incubators, venture capitalists as well as private donors seeking businesses either involved in an acceleration or incubator programme as well as those requiring capital.

The benefits and impacts of YAS! Is so invaluable and could not have come at a better time for the continent and its youth population. Through resources and educational programming gears towards the youth, the initiative is promoting opportunities for some of the continent's most vulnerable and disadvantaged population group. By offering much needed information and technical knowledge on key concepts of enterprise development, initiatives such as YAS! is helping to be a continent where young people are more open to entrepreneurship as a viable alternative

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to trying to secure formal employment in the public or private sector which is often very hard to come by given the size of African economies and the amount of people entering the job market each year. The portal provides services such as business plan development and aims to create an ecosystem map for start-ups and corporates, which will locate and connect various entrepreneurial service providers across Africa. Young African entrepreneurs are now afforded an opportunity to implement their innovation, apply for financing as well as network and pitch their innovative entrepreneurial ideas and projects with potential partners and financiers.

For a large number of young people on the continent, addressing social and economic issues, such as poverty eradicating, accessing decent employment remains a paramount issue of concern.

African governments and the private sector have and continue to struggle in creating enough decent employment for the continent's burgeoning youth population (International Labour Organization, 2017).

For decades, African youth entrepreneurs have run small-scale businesses to support their families and themselves, make a small profit and generate employment opportunities.

With the digital revolution ushering in a new and expanding wave of young entrepreneurs that seek to provide sustainable sources of livelihoods, innovative programs and projects (JA Worldwide and Citi Foundation, 2014), such as YAS! are well placed to maximize the entrepreneurship opportunities found on the continent and promises to providing the needed support services to help reduce poverty and helping governments attain Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development.

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